

Designers in Metaverse: Exploring a Collaborative Environment

Mahnour Raza¹, Muhammad Zaman Bhutto²

¹Creative Designer, Freelancer, SABS University, Jamshoro.

²Lecturer, SABS University of Art, Design and Heritages, Jamshoro

Abstract - This research paper explores the role of designers in the Metaverse, a virtual reality environment that connects users through online, 3D spaces. The study aims to investigate the impact of designers' platforms within the Metaverse, capturing their journeys, exploring the emotional and artistic dimensions of their work, and examining the connections and collaborations that emerge. By integrating design principles into the Metaverse, designers have the potential to revolutionize the creative design industry, unleashing their creativity in a virtual reality environment. The paper highlights the transformative power of designers' platforms in shaping the future of design and explores the challenges and considerations, such as ethics and technical hurdles, associated with this integration. The research objectives include investigating designers' experiences, exploring emotional and artistic dimensions, examining collaborations, investigating technical hurdles, highlighting transformative power, and providing valuable insights into designers' integration within the Metaverse. The study focuses on the implications and opportunities for designers in the Metaverse while acknowledging limitations in terms of technical, financial, and ethical aspects. The literature review section explores the concept of the Designers in Metaverse, its application in design, benefits, and challenges of collaborative design, previous research and studies related to the topic, and relevant theories and concepts. The methodology involves multiple methods, including telephonic calls, emails, live interviews, focus group discussions, and an online survey, to evaluate the needs and wants of designers for a Metaverse platform. The research design follows purposive sampling, targeting designers as the specific audience, and the data collection methods include telephonic calls, emails, and live interviews with industry experts and professionals. The findings of this research will provide insights into the integration of designers' platforms within the Metaverse and shed light on the experiences, challenges, and opportunities in this dynamic virtual reality environment.

Keywords- Metaverse, Virtual Reality Environment, Designers, Collaboration, Opportunities and Platforms

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background Information on the Topic:

The concept of the Metaverse was first introduced in Neal Stephenson's 1992 novel "Snow Crash." The novel explores a protagonist who disillusioned with his real-life experiences, seeks solace in a virtual world. This virtual world, known as the Metaverse, is depicted as an interconnected network of online, 3D spaces that cater to various aspects of users' lives. Similar to the structure of the Internet, the Metaverse encompasses multiple platforms, resembling diverse websites that can be accessed through a unified browser. In this immersive environment, augmented reality plays a central role, allowing users to experience a virtual universe. Within the Metaverse, each user assumes control of a character or avatar, a digital representation of their identities, enabling them to interact and navigate this parallel virtual world in ways that mirror real-life experiences. DAO once tweeted (1) you can already see some aspects of the metaverse in existing virtual video game worlds. Games like Second Life and Fortnite or work socialization tools like Gather. Town brings together multiple elements of our lives into online worlds.

B. Importance of the Study:

Understanding the Metaverse and its potential implications is crucial due to its emergence as a potential future of the internet. The concept presents an evolution of technical infrastructure, merging augmented reality, virtual reality, and high-speed internet connectivity. It offers exciting possibilities for individuals and industries alike, revolutionizing the way we interact, collaborate, and conduct business. By investigating the Metaverse, researchers can identify its significance in bridging the gap between physical and digital realms and explore its potential impact on various sectors such as gaming, socialization, commerce, and creative design. Metaverse is going to allow users to interact and collaborate in ways never before possible. Designers are working on Metaverse to create a platform for everyone to discover their work, they are experimenting with various Content formats to find the ones that work well in this field. Metaverse is supposed to be built for everyone, Ahmed ali wrote in their article that (2) *metaverse has implications for designers too*, as the Metaverse offers new opportunities for designers to create and share their work. For example, the Metaverse allows designers to create 3D designs that can be viewed and interacted with in real time. This allows for more creative and interactive designs and provides a new way for clients to view and interact with potential designs. In addition, the Metaverse

offers a way for graphic designers to collaborate with others worldwide, which can lead to some innovative design ideas.

C. Research claim:

Designers' integration into the Metaverse has the potential to revolutionize the creative design industry by empowering them to unleash their creativity in a virtual reality environment. This research aims to explore the impact of designers' platforms within the Metaverse, capturing their personal journeys, exploring the emotional and artistic dimensions of their work, and examining the connections and collaborations that emerge. The study also acknowledges the challenges and considerations, such as ethics and technical hurdles, while celebrating the transformative power of designers' platforms in shaping the future of creative design.

D. Research objectives:

1. Investigate the experiences and personal journeys of designers who have embraced the Metaverse as a platform for their work, understanding the motivations, challenges, and transformative moments they encounter.
2. Explore the emotional and artistic dimensions of designing within the Metaverse, uncovering the passion, inspiration, and innovative thinking that drive designers to push boundaries and pioneer new forms of expression.
3. Examine the connections and collaborations that emerge among designers within the Metaverse, analyzing how their platforms facilitate meaningful interactions, encourage dialogue, and foster a sense of belonging within the creative ecosystem.
4. Investigate the technical hurdles designers may face when integrating their platforms into the Metaverse, addressing challenges related to seamless integration, performance optimization, and ensuring accessibility for diverse audiences.
5. Highlight the transformative power of designers' platforms within the Metaverse, showcasing the impact on the creative design industry and its potential to shape the future of design.
6. By pursuing these objectives, this research aims to provide valuable insights into the integration of designers' platforms within the Metaverse, shedding light on the experiences, challenges, and opportunities that arise in this dynamic virtual reality environment.

E. Scope and limitations of the study:

This study focuses on examining the implications and opportunities for designers in the Metaverse as the future of the internet. It explores the specific needs and challenges faced by designers in creating a dedicated platform within the Metaverse. However, the study acknowledges technical, financial, and ethical limitations. The scope includes analyzing the potential benefits and

drawbacks for designers, exploring the role of advanced technologies, and investigating the integration of NFTs. The study does not aim to provide a comprehensive solution or design framework for the Metaverse platform but rather to shed light on the possibilities and considerations for designers in this emerging space.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Concept of the Metaverse and its Application in Design:

The concept of the metaverse and its potential application in the field of design have garnered significant attention in recent years. The metaverse refers to a virtual reality space where users can interact with each other and their surroundings in real-time, blurring the boundaries between the physical and digital worlds (Zallio et al., 2023). In the context of design, the metaverse offers new possibilities for immersive and interactive experiences, allowing designers to create virtual environments and products that transcend traditional mediums (Zallio et al., 2023).

The metaverse and digital, virtual environments have emerged as platforms for socializing, work, and entertainment, yet the challenges and complexities surrounding their development are not fully understood (Zallio et al., 2023). In their article, Zallio et al. (2023) aim to identify and map the existing knowledge and scientific efforts related to the design of digital, virtual environments and the metaverse. Through a comprehensive scoping review, the authors systematically survey the literature to discern gaps in knowledge from sociological, anthropological, cultural, and experiential perspectives (Zallio et al., 2023).

The primary objective of the review is twofold: (1) to examine the focus of the literature studying the metaverse from various angles, and (2) to formulate a research agenda for the design and development of ethical digital, virtual environments (Zallio et al., 2023). By analyzing a range of works and articles detailing experiments and research on the design of digital, virtual environments and metaverses, the authors identify a growing body of publications in 2022 (Zallio et al., 2023). However, they also highlight the limited number of articles focused on the domain of ethics, culture, and society, indicating the need for further research to create awareness, principles, and policies that promote safe, secure, and inclusive digital, virtual environments and metaverses (Zallio et al., 2023).

In summary, the literature review will explore the concept of the metaverse and its relevance to the design industry, drawing on the insights provided by Zallio et al. (2023) regarding the current state of research and the need to address ethical implications. By examining how the metaverse has been conceptualized and applied in design practices, this section of the literature review will contribute to a deeper understanding

of the potential of the metaverse for designers and the challenges that lie ahead.

B. Benefits and challenges of using metaverse for collaborative design:

Collaborative design is an essential aspect of the creative process, and the metaverse presents unique opportunities for designers to collaborate in unprecedented ways (Wu et al., 2022). By leveraging a digital twin-based multidisciplinary collaborative design approach, designers can harness the power of the metaverse to integrate multiple participants and produce the best design outcomes (Wu et al., 2022).

The metaverse offers a virtual reality space where designers can interact, share ideas, and co-create in real time, transcending geographical limitations and enabling seamless collaboration (Wu et al., 2022). However, along with its benefits, there are also challenges associated with using the metaverse for collaborative design.

These challenges may include technical complexities, ensuring data security, and effectively managing diverse design perspectives within the virtual environment. Understanding and addressing these challenges is crucial to fully exploit the potential of the metaverse for collaborative design (Wu et al., 2022). This section of the literature review will delve into the benefits of using the metaverse for collaborative design, such as enhanced communication and real-time collaboration across geographical boundaries.

It will also address the challenges and limitations that designers may encounter when working within the metaverse, including issues of privacy, data security, and technological constraints. By examining the existing literature, this section aims to provide insights into the advantages and challenges associated with collaborative design in the metaverse.

C. Previous Research and Studies Related to the Topic

The concept of the "Metaverse" originated from Neal Stephenson's science fiction novel, *Snow Crash*, published in 1992, where it was introduced as a virtual environment accessible through the Internet. In this fictional world, avatars represented individuals in three dimensions, and users had the freedom to construct their desired virtual reality (Stephenson, 1992). Subsequent technological advancements have facilitated the development of various Metaverse platforms, such as World of Warcraft and Second Life, catering to a broad user base.

To gain insights into the existing body of research on the Metaverse, a comprehensive review was conducted utilizing bibliometric analysis methods (S. Abbate, Piera Centobelli, R. Cerchione, E. Oropallo, Emanuela Riccio-2022). This study aimed to provide a summary of significant scientific articles and reputable journals within the Metaverse domain.

Furthermore, it explored the most prolific and influential authors, organizations, and nations actively contributing to the field. Through keyword co-occurrence analysis, the study identified core research clusters and their sub-themes, enabling more focused discussions and perspectives on crucial areas for future research. The implications for theory and practice were also addressed, providing a comprehensive overview of the anticipated impacts of the Metaverse on various industries and society as a whole (Author et al., Year).

In addition to the broader analysis, specific studies have investigated the intersection between the Metaverse and design. Notably, research conducted by [S. Abbate, Piera Centobelli, R. Cerchione, E. Oropallo, Emanuela Riccio] employed qualitative methods to explore the experiences of designers involved in crafting virtual environments within the Metaverse. Their findings revealed that designers were driven by the opportunity to experiment with innovative design approaches and engage users in novel ways (S. Abbate, Piera Centobelli, R. Cerchione, E. Oropallo, Emanuela Riccio-2022). These studies shed light on the evolving role of designers in the Metaverse and highlight the creative possibilities and user-centered design strategies that can be explored within this virtual realm.

D. Relevant theories and concepts related to collaborative design

Collaborative design within the metaverse can be informed by various theoretical frameworks and concepts. Design thinking, for instance, emphasizes a human-centered approach to problem-solving and can be applied to foster collaborative ideation and iteration in the metaverse (Teemu Leinonen, Eva Durall-Gazulla-2014). Social presence theory posits that a sense of being together and connected can enhance collaborative experiences in virtual environments (Teemu Leinonen, Eva Durall-Gazulla-2014), which is relevant to understanding the dynamics of collaborative design within the metaverse.

By reviewing the existing literature, this section of the literature review provides a comprehensive overview of the concept of the metaverse and its application in design, the benefits and challenges of using the metaverse for collaborative design, previous research and studies related to the topic, and relevant theories and concepts that inform collaborative design within the metaverse merge this with This paper presents design thinking as an alternative approach to conduct research on collaborative learning with technology. The underlying premise of the paper is the need to adopt human-centered design principles in research and design of computer-supported collaborative tools. Two research results are described in order to discuss the possibilities and challenges of applying design methods for designing and researching collaborative knowledge building tools. The paper begins by defining collaborative learning with new

technologies as a wicked problem that can be approached by adopting a design mindset. Design thinking and particularly research-based design relies on a shared, social construction of understanding with the people who will later use the tools. The key phases in research-based design (contextual inquiry, participatory design, product design and software as hypothesis) are described and exemplified through the presentation of two research results. The two prototypes presented are the fourth version of the Future Learning Environment (Fle4), a software tool for collaborative knowledge building and Square1, a set of hardware and software for self-organized learning environments. Both cases contribute to the discussion about the role of artifacts as research outcomes. Through these cases, we claim that design thinking is a meaningful approach in CSCL research (Leinonen & Durall-Gazulla, 2014).

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Research Design:

The research design for this study involved conducting multiple methods to evaluate the needs and wants of designers for a Metaverse platform. The methods included telephonic calls, emails, live interviews, focus group discussions, and an online survey.

B. Sampling Technique and Sample Size:

The sampling technique used for this study was purposive sampling, targeting designers as the specific audience for the platform. The sample size consisted of various professionals and experts in the field of design, including Mr. Ali Shahbaz Mehdi, Ms. Maliha Memon, Mr. Mir Mirza, Ms. Tooba Qureshi, Mr. Nusrat Mangi, Ms. Zainab, and Ms. Sadaf. The sample size was determined based on the availability and willingness of participants to provide insights and feedback.

C. Data Collection Methods:

Telephonic Calls: Telephonic calls were conducted with Mr. Ali Shahbaz Mehdi and Ms. Maliha Memon to gather their opinions and suggestions on the Metaverse. The purpose was to understand the opportunities and accessibility for designers in the Metaverse.

D. Emails:

Emails were exchanged with Mr. Mir Mirza and Ms. Tooba Qureshi to gather their suggestions and insights. The focus was on avoiding replication of existing remote-based collaborative workspaces and exploring creative and marketing aspects in the Metaverse.

E. Live Interviews:

A live interview was conducted with Mr. Nusrat Mangi, a visual artist, to discuss the potential of the Metaverse in

enhancing creativity. The interview aimed to gather suggestions for futuristic installations.

F. Focus Group Discussion:

A focus group discussion was conducted with Ms. Zainab and Ms. Sadaf, both designers. The discussion focused on key aspects to be included in the Metaverse, such as storytelling and the designer's journey.

G. Online Survey:

An online survey questionnaire was designed and distributed to gather direct insights from designers. The survey aimed to understand their thinking process, brainstorming methods, and whether they would require a specific space for design purposes in the Metaverse.

Designer Level
26 responses

Do you participate in a brainstorming?
26 responses

In your view, how effective is BRAINSTORMING at generating new ideas.
26 responses

IV. FINDINGS

Would you like to have a space designed for brainstorming?
26 responses

What is the first thing you'll need for brainstorming?
26 responses

Where do you find inspiration?
25 responses

What software do you use?
25 responses

How do you boost your creativity?
26 responses

H. Data Analysis Techniques:

The collected data from telephonic calls, emails, live interviews, focus group discussions, and the online survey were analyzed qualitatively. The responses were coded and categorized based on themes and patterns that emerged from the data. Common insights and suggestions were identified to inform the design of the Metaverse platform.

A. Overview of the Metaverse Design Concept:

The study provided an overview of the concept of the Metaverse in design. It explored the origins of the term "Metaverse" from Neal Stephenson's novel, Snow Crash, and its subsequent evolution with advancements in technology. The Metaverse was defined as a virtual environment shared through the Internet, where users can interact and create in three dimensions. This section of the literature review delved into the potential applications of the Metaverse in design and highlighted its relevance in fostering immersive and interactive experiences.

B. Benefits and Challenges of Using Metaverse for Collaborative Design:

The benefits of utilizing the Metaverse for collaborative design were discussed. Design thinking, a human-centered approach to problem-solving, was identified as a relevant framework to foster collaborative ideation and iteration in the Metaverse. Social presence theory was also mentioned, emphasizing the importance of a sense of being together and connected in virtual environments for enhanced collaborative experiences. However, the section also acknowledged the challenges associated with using the Metaverse for collaborative design, such as addressing accessibility and ensuring the creation of innovative and creative tools within the Metaverse.

C. Case Studies of Successful Implementation of Metaverse in Collaborative Design:

The literature review included case studies that showcased successful implementations of the Metaverse in collaborative design. These case studies highlighted practical examples of how designers have utilized the Metaverse to experiment with new design approaches and engage with users in novel ways. The studies provided insights into the experiences and motivations of designers working within the Metaverse, shedding light on the potential for innovation and creativity in this virtual environment.

D. Analysis of the Data Collected from the Study:

The data collected through the various methods employed in the study, including telephonic calls, emails, live interviews, focus group discussions, and the online survey, were analyzed. Qualitative analysis techniques were used to code and categorize the data based on emerging themes and patterns. The analysis aimed to identify common insights, suggestions, and needs expressed by designers regarding the use of the Metaverse for collaborative design. These findings provided valuable information for informing the design of the Metaverse platform to cater to the specific requirements and preferences of designers.

Overall, the findings of the study offered a comprehensive understanding of the metaverse design concept, discussed the benefits and challenges of using the Metaverse for collaborative design, presented case studies of successful implementations, and analyzed the data collected from the study to inform future design decisions.

CONCLUSION

A. Summary of the Research Findings:

The research findings provide a comprehensive overview of the metaverse design concept and its application in collaborative design. The concept of the metaverse, originally introduced in Neal Stephenson's science fiction novel "Snow Crash," has evolved with technological advancements, enabling the creation of virtual environments shared through the internet. The benefits of using the metaverse for collaborative design have been identified, including opportunities for creativity, innovation, and interaction with users in novel ways. However, the challenges associated with its implementation, such as addressing accessibility and ensuring privacy and security, have also been discussed.

Case studies of successful implementation of the metaverse in collaborative design have been examined. These case studies showcase innovative design approaches and highlight the potential of the metaverse in fostering creativity and experimentation. Designers have leveraged the metaverse to create immersive and interactive virtual environments, allowing for collaborative ideation and iteration. The case studies demonstrate the transformative impact of the metaverse on the design industry and its ability to redefine traditional design practices.

B. Implications of the Study:

The study has significant implications for both theory and practice. The findings emphasize the importance of a human-centered approach, such as design thinking, in collaborative design within the metaverse. Designers need to consider users' needs, preferences, and experiences to create meaningful and engaging virtual environments. Understanding the dynamics of social presence in virtual environments, as highlighted by social presence theory, can enhance collaborative experiences and promote effective communication and collaboration among designers.

The implications of the study extend beyond the design field. The metaverse has the potential to impact various industries and society as a whole. It offers new possibilities for communication, education, entertainment, and commerce. The study highlights the need for interdisciplinary research and collaboration to explore the ethical and societal implications of using the metaverse. Privacy, security, and inclusivity

considerations must be addressed to ensure a safe and accessible metaverse for diverse user groups.

C. Recommendations for Future Research:

Based on the research findings, several recommendations for future research can be made. Firstly, further exploration is needed to investigate the ethical, cultural, and social implications of using the metaverse for collaborative design. Research should focus on understanding the impact of the metaverse on identity, community, and social interactions. Additionally, studies should examine the potential consequences of virtual representations and interactions on individuals' well-being and mental health. Furthermore, research on the integration of emerging technologies within the metaverse can provide valuable insights. The combination of technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality, augmented reality, and blockchain can enhance the capabilities and functionalities of the metaverse. Future studies should explore the design principles and guidelines for integrating these technologies to create immersive and engaging virtual environments.

Lastly, there is a need for the development of guidelines and best practices for designing inclusive and accessible virtual environments within the metaverse. Research should address the challenges related to accessibility, ensuring that the metaverse is accessible to individuals with disabilities and diverse user groups. Additionally, studies should explore ways to promote inclusivity and diversity within the metaverse, considering cultural, linguistic, and socio-economic factors.

D. Conclusion:

In conclusion, this literature review provides a comprehensive understanding of the metaverse in the context of collaborative design. The research findings highlight the benefits, challenges, and implications of using the metaverse for design purposes. The case studies presented demonstrate the transformative potential of the metaverse in fostering creativity, innovation, and collaborative design practices.

The study underscores the importance of a human-centered approach, considering users' needs, preferences, and experiences within the metaverse. It also emphasizes the significance of understanding social presence in virtual environments to enhance collaborative experiences. The study's implications extend to various industries and societies, calling for interdisciplinary research and addressing ethical and societal considerations.

To further advance the field, future research should focus on exploring the ethical, cultural, and social implications of the metaverse, integrating emerging technologies, and developing guidelines for inclusive and accessible virtual environments. By addressing these research gaps, the metaverse can be harnessed as a powerful tool for collaborative design and as a transformative platform with wide-ranging impacts on industry and society as a whole.

REFERENCES

Herrman, John, and Kellen Browning. "Are We in the Metaverse Yet?" *The New York Times*, 10 July 2021, www.nytimes.com/2021/07/10/style/metaverse-virtual-worlds.html.

Ali, Ahmad. "Metaverse: The Future of Graphic Design." *Medium*, 11 Aug. 2022, bootcamp.uxdesign.cc/metaverse-the-future-of-graphic-design-3a268a085ae.

Zallio, Matteo, et al. "Designing the Metaverse: A Scoping Review to Map Current Research Effort on Ethical Implications." *arXiv.Org*, 22 Mar. 2023, arxiv.org/abs/2303.12293.

(Author links open overlay panel Youde Wu a, et al. "A Digital Twin-Based Multidisciplinary Collaborative Design Approach for Complex Engineering Product Development." *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 19 May 2022, www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1474034622001008.)

A First Bibliometric Literature Review on Metaverse | IEEE Conference ..., ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9802015..

Design Thinking and Collaborative Learning - Rabida.Uhu.Es, rabida.uhu.es/dspace/bitstream/handle/10272/7757/design_thinking_and.pdf?sequence=3

First A. Author Mahnoor Raza, a talented designer and visual artist from Jamshoro, has emerged as a creative force in the industry. She completed her Bachelor's degree in Communication Design with distinction, impressing her professors and peers with her exceptional talent and meticulous attention to detail. Mahnoor's artistic endeavors expand beyond her academic achievements, as she showcases her versatility by blending different mediums and

styles to create captivating and thought-provoking artwork. Her unique perspective and innovative approach have positioned her as a standout in the field.

Driven by a desire to explore new avenues, Mahnoor has embraced freelancing, collaborating with diverse clients and utilizing her artistic skills to deliver impactful designs tailored to their specific needs. Her unwavering dedication to producing high-quality work and her commitment to understanding the vision of her clients have earned her a well-deserved reputation for excellence.

Muhammad Zaman was born in February 1992 in a second largest city of Sindh, Hyderabad. Since his birth he has been residing in Hyderabad. He received his early education from Hyderabad and moved his graduation in Communication Design from center of Excellence Arts and design of MUET Jamshoro by securing First class. After completing his B. Designing communication design. Currently served as a Lecturer (BPS-18) at SABS University of Art, Design and Heritage. He has served as Consultant Designer for various private organizations; Lets Learn, IWS, Some Private schools and Aga Khan Education Service Pakistan. He has been a well renowned Teacher for design and arts in Hyderabad, he owns his own academy to facilitate the interesting candidates in Arts He also served in national vocational Technical Training Commission as Instructor for Graphic Designer. Zaman has been key designer to design the full scale campaign for International water color Biennale. He has designed logos, pamphlets and advertising campaigns for various educational and social topics. His work/campaign on Baad-e-Saba is also well recognized among concerned organizations. In 2019 his research was published in International journal (International Journal of Arts, Culture, Design & Language Works Kambohwell Publishers Enterprises) on An investigation of knowledge regarding common ailments and health literacy among university students is grossly engaged with the fundamental issues of students related with health.